

Security and privacy management in the intelligent transportation systems

* Indicates required question

The CHES project

The *Cyber-security Excellence Hub in Estonia and South Moravia (CHES)* aims to integrate leading cybersecurity institutions and capitalize on the strengths of both regions to address important Europe-wide challenges. CHES follows the strategies and roadmaps of the European Cybersecurity Competence Pilots and builds on the experience of CHES partners involved in all four of these pilots, contributing to the safe transition of the EU to a full-scale digital society. The CHES Hub conducts a thorough needs analysis of the two regions and develops a joint cross-border R&I strategy for cybersecurity. CHES is Horizon Europe project, which is funded by European Commission (more details can be found [here](#) and on our website <https://chess-eu.cs.ut.ee/>).

Purpose of the survey

This survey aims to define the up-to-date state of security and privacy management in intelligent infrastructure systems in Estonia and South Moravia. The second step will be comparing the region's state with the baseline measures. We plan to conduct an empirical study to explore what policies, approaches, methods and techniques for information security and privacy management are used in organizations and how they have supported the transformation of the business towards reliance on the intelligent infrastructure system.

Who should participate?

The focus of the study is on the companies in the transportation sector, including but not limited to those that enable ride-hailing, vehicle sharing, smart parking, V2X communication, roadside units, ITS sensors, and systems/subsystems for ITS processing/monitoring/management. Companies may develop solutions/systems/devices for ITS and/or use intelligent transportation systems for their operations.

Survey participants need to have a good understanding of the IT system stack and be aware of internal (organisational) realities.

The survey takes about 20 minutes to complete.

Confidentiality

Your input data will be treated and remain strictly confidential. The data will be only used for research purposes and will be published in aggregated form. You are also free to withdraw your participation from our research at any time without reason. If you don't want to answer a question, you can choose the "I don't know" option.

What will you get from participation?

All respondents providing their organisation name and email (optional) will get early access to survey aggregated results and project outputs. Thus, respondents will get the assessment results of the security and privacy measures with respect to the state-of-the-art solutions and recommendations for the company. Survey participants will also be invited to participate in the CHESS project's free cybersecurity trainings and other raising awareness events.

1. By participating, you understand and agree that the data and information gathered during this study may be used by the CHESS academic partners for publication purposes. However, any identifiable information will not be mentioned in any such publication or dissemination of the research data and/or results.

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I agree to participate in the survey as representative of the company I work for.

Contact information

2. Name

3. E-mail

General questions about the company

In this section, we ask you to fill in general information about your company, so that researchers are able to define the sector profile of your company.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

4. 1.1. What is your organisation's name?

5. 1.2. What is your position/role in the organization?

Tick all that apply.

- Information security officer
- CTO
- Product owner/manager/analyst
- System analyst
- Process owner/manager/analyst
- Project manager
- Software architect
- CEO
- IT manager
- Other: _____

6. 1.3. Where does your company primarily operate? *

Mark only one oval.

- Estonia
- South Moravia (Czechia)
- Other: _____

7. 1.4. For which purposes does your company use IT system(s)? *

Tick all that apply.

- We don't use any
- Only for storing data digitally
- For customer management
- For enterprise resource management
- Digital solutions for end-users
- Exchanging data with external IT systems

8. 1.5. Would you call the system used in your company "an intelligent transportation system"?

In this and the following sections, we use the term '*intelligent transportation system (ITS)*' that refer to the advanced applications which without embodying intelligence as such aim to provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated and 'smarter' use of transport networks

Mark only one oval.

Not at all

0

1

2

3

4

Yes, our system is an intelligent transportation system

9. 1.6. In which area does your company primarily operate? (select all that apply) *

Tick all that apply.

- Smart Parking
- Vehicle sharing (incl. scooter-sharing, bicycle sharing, car-pooling)
- Ride-hailing
- Connected vehicles (i.e. vehicular network, V2X communication)
- Electric vehicle charging
- Traffic management (incl. road and railway)
- Electronic Toll Collection
- Other: _____

10. 1.7. How many active end-users does your digital solution have in the selected region?

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 1,000
- 1,001 – 10,000
- 10,001 – 100,000
- 100,001 – 1,000,000
- More than 1,000,000
- Not applicable
- I don't know

Section "Organisation"

The following questions are related to the *organisation's design and strategy*.

The questions aim to define how the organisation's strategy guides the processes based on the strategic objectives, how the organisational design and strategy itself are guided by the external factors (e.g., legal and regulatory provisions), how the organisation's structure peoples by the established culture towards information security, and how the organisation's strategy drives the architecture of the technical security measures.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

11. 2.1. What is the main objective of your intelligent transportation system? *

Mark only one oval.

- Decreasing the traffic congestion
- Resolving the problem of air pollution
- Improvement of the city services
- Improved management of parking facilities
- Enabling on-demand mobility
- Optimizing driver's time spent on parking
- Optimisation of parking spaces usage
- Preventing unauthorized occupation of the parking spot
- I don't know
- Other: _____

12. 2.2. How much is your company involved in the lifecycle of your intelligent transportation system? *

Mark only one oval.

- We use the ready-to-use solution which is not under development
- We use the ready-to-use solution which is continuously updated by the system provider
- We use services of the outsourcing company(s) who manages the system we use
- We use services of the outsourcing company(s) who continuously updates the system based on our needs
- There is a small development/support team who manage the system in-house which was developed by external service provider
- We have a development team that is fully responsible for the system, its support and development
- I don't know

13. 2.3. How much has your system changed during the last 5 years? *

Mark only one oval.

- Not changed at all
- There are minor changes to the main functionality; active support of the existing system
- There are major changes to the main functionality; active support and development of the existing system
- There are major changes in the system and its components
- There are major changes in the system and its components due to the integrations with external system(s)
- A new system has been developed separately from the old system
- I don't know

14. 2.4. With how many external systems is your system integrated? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-2
- 3-4
- 5+
- I don't know

15. 2.5. What are the challenges your company faces during the usage/development/support of your intelligent transportation system? (select all that apply)

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Tick all that apply.

- Addressing data privacy and security of users' data in order to prevent identity and trajectory leakage
- The balance between privacy and efficiency of the system
- Absence or lack of industry regulations and/or standards
- Following the data minimization principle
- Providing the expected level of system security before the system is launched
- Interoperability with other systems and/or providers
- Absence of national strategy for developing smart environments
- Resource-constrained devices usage
- Heterogeneous network
- High expectations from such system quality characteristics (e.g., platform independence, OS independence, exchangeability, cross-layer algorithms, scalability and efficiency)
- I don't know
- Other: _____

16. 2.6. What kind of information is used within your intelligent transportation system? (select all that apply or specify in "Other")

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Tick all that apply.

- Parking/Ride/Toll transaction
- Other aggregated data based on the transactions history
- Driver's identity
- Driver's location
- Driver's transactions history
- Driver's payment details
- Available parking spaces
- Available tolls
- Passenger's identity
- Passenger' transactions history
- Passenger's payment details
- Vehicle's location
- Vehicle's state details
- Vehicle's identity
- I don't know
- Other: _____

17. 2.7. Which security or privacy-related legislation and/or regulations affect your intelligent transportation system? *
(select all that apply)

Tick all that apply.

- General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR)
- European Union directive 2010/40/EU (7 July 2010) (a.k.a. ITS Directive)
- Consumer protection directives 2019/770 and 2019/771
- UNECE regulation No 155 Cyber security and cyber security management system (from 2020)
- Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 of the European Parliament and of the Council
- Regulation (EU) 2018/858 of the European Parliament and of the Council
- I don't know
- Other: _____

18. 2.8. Which cyber/information security standard(s) does your organisation follow? *

Tick all that apply.

- No standards are applicable to our intelligent transportation system
- Estonian Information Security Standard
- Předpis 181/2014 Sb. (zákon o kybernetické bezpečnosti)
- ISO 27001
- ISO 27002
- Other standards from ISO/IEC 27000-series
- NIST Special Publications (e.g. NIST SP 800-39, NIST SP 800-37)
- ETSI standards series (e.g. ETSI TS 102 941, 102 731, 103 097)
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 1"

The following questions are related to the stakeholders of your intelligent transportation system (ITS) as well as policies & practices your organisation you.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

19. 3.1. Who are the stakeholders of your products/services the intelligent transportation system? *
(select all that apply)

Tick all that apply.

- Passenger
- Driver
- Parking Service Provider
- Trusted Authority (who issues credentials)
- Parking/Toll Officer
- City Government
- Time-stamping authority
- System provider (in case you use external systems based on the service-level agreement)
- Your organisation employee
- I don't know
- Other: _____

20. 3.2. What are the practices and policies used for assuring information security and/or privacy management in your company? *
(select all the apply)

Tick all that apply.

- Following the selected risk management framework
- Following the selected security framework
- National (cyber) security strategy
- Threat modelling
- Penetration testing
- Security Development Lifecycle
- We don't use any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

21. 3.3. How much security development is integrated into your system lifecycle? *
(select the most relevant)

Mark only one oval.

- We assume our system is secure as it is launched and does not update
- The system is updated with ad-hoc security patches if the system was attacked
- The system is updated with ad-hoc security patches regularly
- The system is updated with security patches regularly
- Security team is continuously working on security and privacy measures
- I don't know

22. 3.4. Which information security and privacy training are established for your system users? *

Tick all that apply.

- Introducing the privacy policy during the first-time onboarding to the system
- Introducing the information security measure of the system that concerns their data or behaviour
- Regular reminders about privacy policy aspects
- Phishing training
- We don't have any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

23. 3.5. Which information security and privacy training are established for the employees in your organisation? *

Tick all that apply.

- Cyber hygiene trainings
- Trainings for raising awareness about security threats
- Data protection trainings
- We don't have any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 2"

The following questions are related to the technological profile of your organisation.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

24. 4.1. Which of the following architectural measures are used in your intelligent transportation system? *
- (select all that apply)

Tick all that apply.

- Blockchain-based system
- Anonymous authentication
- Storage of sensitive personal data on the data subject device (e.g., passenger, driver)
- Secret-sharing
- Multi-party computation (MPC)
- Securing data in transit
- We don't use any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

25. 4.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for authentication and access control? *

Tick all that apply.

- Role-based access control
- Anonymous credential system
- Attribute-based credentials and access control
- 2-factor authentication
- RFID authentication
- Biometric-based authentication
- Pseudorandom identity assignment
- Public Key Infrastructure
- We don't use any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

26. 4.3. Which measures are used in your intelligent transportation system for secure communication between parties? *

Tick all that apply.

- TLS protocol
- IPSec protocol
- VPN solution
- Other secured communication protocol
- Customer end-to-end encryption
- Custom asymmetric encryption
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Other: _____

27. 4.4. Which cryptographic measures are used in your intelligent transportation system? *

Tick all that apply.

- RSA digital signature
- Homomorphic encryption
- Zero-Knowledge Proof
- Oblivious pseudorandom function (OPRF)
- Trusted execution environment (TEE)
- Private set intersection (PSI)
- Blind signature
- Elliptic curve cryptography
- Diffie-Hellman group key exchange
- Hash-based message authentication codes
- Oblivious transfer protocol
- We don't use any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality"

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you intelligent infrastructure system.

28. 4.5.1. Do you have **navigation/routing** functionality in your intelligent transportation system? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 32*
- No *Skip to question 29*

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality"

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you intelligent infrastructure system.

29. 4.6.1. Do you have **payment** functionality in your intelligent transportation system? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 33*

No *Skip to question 30*

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality"

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you intelligent infrastructure system.

30. 4.7.1. Do you have **location-based search** in your intelligent transportation system? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 34*

No *Skip to question 31*

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality"

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you intelligent infrastructure system.

31. 4.8.1. Do you have functionality of **pass/reservation document creation** in your intelligent transportation system? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 35*

No *Skip to question 36*

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Navigation/routing"

Measures for protecting navigation/routing

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

32. 4.5.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for navigation/routing? *

Tick all that apply.

Privacy-preserving navigation systems

Location obfuscation (hiding the exact location by adding noise)

Not applicable

Other: _____

Skip to question 29

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Payment"

Measures for protecting payments

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

33. 4.6.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for payment? *

Tick all that apply.

- Card-based payment
- Token-based payment
- Anonymous payment
- Automated payment using smart contract
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Skip to question 30

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Location-based search"

Measures for protecting location-based search

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

34. 4.7.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for parking slot/toll/vehicle search? *

Tick all that apply.

- Private information retrieval
- Hashmap storing of parking slot/toll/vehicle locations
- Search based on the exact location
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Skip to question 31

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Pass/reservation document"

Measures for protecting pass/reservation document

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

35. 4.8.2. Which technologies are used in your intelligent transportation system for ticket generation, parking or ride reservation? *

Tick all that apply.

- Blind signature
- Anonymous reservation/ticket
- Presenting proof-of-knowledge
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Other"

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

36. 4.9. What are the other security- or privacy-preserving technologies used in your intelligent transportation system which was not mentioned? *

37. 4.10. Do you consider employing post-quantum cryptography in the future in your intelligent infrastructure system? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, we already employ this
- Yes (within 1 - 3 years)
- Yes (in 3+ years)
- No
- I do not know

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 4: Processes"

The following questions are related to processes established for managing your intelligent infrastructure system.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

38. 5.1. Which of the following principles are used during your system development/support? *

(select all that apply)

Tick all that apply.

- Privacy by design
- Privacy-related testing and verification
- Data minimisation
- Secure programming
- Usage of sensor devices which have built-in security measures
- We don't use any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

39. 5.2. Which network security measures are used for your intelligent transportation system support? *

Tick all that apply.

- Intrusion detection system
- Security incident and event management systems (SEIM)
- Behavioural analytics system
- Network traffic analyser
- Vulnerability scanner
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Follow-up questions about this survey

40. How would you assess the level of your information system security? *

Mark only one oval.

- Not secure
- Somewhat secure, should be improved
- Secure, but could be improved
- Secured according to up-to-date measures and considering relevant threats
- Very secure

41. Which sources did you use to answer this survey? *

Tick all that apply.

- Documentation (incl. manuals, guidelines, technical documentation, etc.)
- Consultation with colleagues
- My personal knowledge of the system
- My personal knowledge of the organisation
- Other: _____

42. How easy was it for you to find the information asked in this survey? *

Mark only one oval.

- To answer all of the questions, I had to consult with colleagues or documents
- To answer most of the questions, I had to consult with colleagues or documents
- To answer some questions, I had to consult with colleagues or documents
- To answer few questions, I had to consult with colleagues or documents
- To answer questions, I did not consult with any colleagues or documents

43. Would you like to participate in free training/workshops organized by CHESSE partners in following topics? *

Tick all that apply.

- Applied cryptography
- Privacy-preserving technologies
- Security certification
- Standards and regulations
- Blockchain and security
- Post-quantum cryptography and security
- Verification of trustworthy software
- Human-centric aspects of security
- We are not interested
- I don't know

44. (Optional) Feedback or comments regarding the survey

Were the questions understandable?

Should some questions be changed, redrafted, or should something be added?

Did any of the questions seem irrelevant?

Do you have any suggestions for improving the survey?
